

TREAT-AD

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PTPN6 (SHP1) Catalytic Domain: Protein Expression, Purification and Crystallization

NCBI Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	5777/P29350
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Date Approved by Admin Core	September 21 st , 2023
Document version	v1
Document version date	September 20, 2023
Citation	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368210
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Introduction: Src homology 2 domain containing phosphatase 1 (SHP1) is a member of protein tyrosine phosphatase (PTP) family of proteins that aids in catalysis of dephosphorylation of phosphotyrosine peptides¹. SHP1 is known to be highly expressed in hematopoietic cells, with its function involved in termination of signal transduction by dephosphorylating substrates such as Lyn, Syk, Lck, ZAP70. SHP1 mediates CD33 signaling, which prevents TREM2 receptor activation thereby preventing microglial phagocytosis. According to International Genomics of Alzheimer's Project (IGAP) genome wide association study (GWAS), CD33 has shown significant association with Late Onset Alzheimer's Disease (LOAD). Exact mechanism of SHP1 mediated TREM2 downregulation is still under investigation. Hence, structural characterization of SHP1 in the presence of small molecule inhibitors will provide more insight into the mechanism of action.

Proteins Purified: Catalytic domain of SHP1 protein with residues 250-531 of wild-type human SHP1 was codon optimized for bacterial expression by GenScript (**Table 1**). This construct also contains an N-terminal, hexa-histidine tag and short amino acid linker (GVDLGT) followed by a Tobacco Etch Virus (TEV) protease cleavage site (ENLYFQ⁻G). The molecular weight of the SHP1 protein construct is 36 kDa. Immobilized metal-ion chromatography (IMAC) step using nickel(II)-charged resin followed by gel filtration chromatography was performed to purify SHP1 protein. The purity of this protein stock is shown in **Figure 1**. Subsequent purification

methods prior to preparation of crystallization are described in more detail below.

Future Plans: We will continue to work on crystallization of SHP1 catalytic domain construct in the presence of small molecule inhibitors. The resulting structures and associated data processing parameters will be uploaded into the online repositories.

References

1. Yang J, Liang X, Niu T, Meng W, Zhao Z, Wayne Zhou G. Crystal Structure of the Catalytic Domain of Protein-Tyrosine Phosphatase SHP-1*.; 1998. <http://www.jbc.org>

Methods:

SHP1 catalytic domain expression vector construction: The gene coding region for the SHP1 catalytic domain with hexa-histidine tag (**Table 1**) was codon-optimized, synthesized and inserted into the pET11a expression vector, which contains a carbenicillin selection marker, by GenScript. The resulting plasmid was sequenced verified by GenScript.

SHP1 catalytic domain expression from E.coli: The SHP1 expression vector was transformed into *E.coli* strain BL21 using electroporation. Transformed cells were transferred to 200µl of SOC medium and incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes at 200rpm. Upon recovery, 50µl of cells was plated onto a fresh LB agar plate with 100 µg/ml carbenicillin, and incubated at 37°C overnight. The following morning, a single colony was picked and used to inoculate a 10 ml culture containing Super LB media. The culture was incubated at 37 °C overnight with shaking. The next morning, 1 ml of the 10 ml culture was added to 50 ml of Super LB media until the OD @600nm reached a value between 0.6-0.8. 1 ml of cells per 1L of Super LB media were then transferred to 2.5L flasks and supplemented with 1 ml of 100 µg/ml carbenicillin, 25 ml of 8% lactose, 10 ml of 60% glycerol, 5 ml of 10% glucose. The flasks were then incubated at 37°C with shaking at 200 rpm until the OD @600nm reached between 0.6-0.8. The flasks were transferred to 18 °C with shaking at 200 rpm and the protein was allowed to be induced overnight through autoinduction. Cells were centrifuged at 13000xg for 15 minutes. Supernatant was discarded and pellets obtained from all the flasks were combined, and the wet weight of the combined pellets was measured. The resulting protein pellet was then resuspended in 5ml of Buffer A/Lysis buffer (see **Table 1**) per gram of cells (wet weight). Cells resuspended in lysis buffer were then lysed by sonication (6s on, 9s off, 60% amplitude) on ice for 15 minutes. Resulting lysate was clarified by centrifuging at 55,000xg for 40 minutes at 4°C, followed by filtering the supernatant through a 0.45µm filter before proceeding with purification.

Immobilized Metal Affinity Chromatography (IMAC) FPLC purification: Clarified cell lysate was applied over a 5 ml Nickel HiTrap HP column (GE Healthcare) using a flow rate of 2 ml/min and an AKTA pure FPLC system. After the entire sample was applied, additional Buffer A was pumped over the column to ensure application of any leftover lysate. The HiTrap HP Column was then washed with Buffer A until the UV absorbance at 280nm reached a stable baseline. The HiTrap HP column was then washed with 10% Buffer B (see **Table 2**) to remove non-specific proteins binders. SHP1 protein was then eluted using 10-100% linear gradient of

Buffer B over 20 column volumes. Protein concentration was determined using the Bio-Rad Bradford assay followed by estimation of protein purity using SDS-PAGE. Fractions containing SHP1 were pooled together and combined with 1 mg of Tobacco-etch virus (TEV) protease for about 100 mg of SHP1 protein to cleave the His-tag. The SHP1 and TEV mixture was placed in a 10k MWCO snakeskin dialysis bag and dialyzed against 2L of dialysis buffer overnight at 4°C. After overnight dialysis, the protein sample was recovered from the dialysis bag and centrifuged at 15,000xg for 15 minutes at 4 °C to remove any precipitate. Recovered supernatant was then loaded onto to a 5ml Nickel HiTrap HP column at a flow rate of 2 ml/min using AKTA pure FPLC system. Flow through was collected using a fraction collector and 10 ml fraction volumes. Once the complete flow-through had been collected, the column was washed with Buffer A until the UV at 280nm reached baseline. Any remaining bound protein was eluted from the column using 100% Buffer B which was also collected using a fraction collector and 10 ml fraction volumes. The concentration and purity of SHP1 was determined using the Bio-Rad Bradford protein assay and SDS-PAGE.

Size Exclusion Chromatography: After recovering the flow-through from the reverse nickel IMAC column, SHP1 protein with its cleaved Hit-tag was concentrated down to 1 to 2ml volume and applied to a 320 ml Superdex 200 26/600 GL column (Cytiva). The column was pre-equilibrated with Storage Buffer (**Table 2**) and the protein sample was pumped over the column using an isocratic flow of Storage Buffer at 2ml/min. 5 ml fractions were collected over one column volume. Peaks containing the SHP1 protein were combined, and the resulting protein concentration was determined using a Biotek Take 3 plate and absorbance at 280 nm and the molar extinction coefficient generated from ExPASy using the amino acid sequence listed in **Table 1**. Final purity of the SHP1 protein samples were checked using SDS-PAGE (**Figure 1**). Purified SHP1 sample was concentrated to 0.7mg/ml and stored at -80 °C for further use.

Crystallization and X-ray data collection: Frozen SHP1 aliquots were thawed out, and the protein was further purified, i.e. ‘polished’ using a 24 ml Superdex 200 10/300 GL column (Cytiva) to remove any protein aggregates. This protein was then used immediately for protein crystallization. Initial crystallization conditions were identified using commercially available kits and setting up sitting drops using a SPTlabtech Mosquito liquid-handling robot. After screening over 3,500 unique crystallization conditions, crystals were obtained from 1.8M AmSO₄, 0.1 MES sodium salt pH 6.5, at 14.8 mg/ml protein concentration. Using that crystallization condition, 24-well hanging-drop trays were setup at 1:1 ratio of protein to reservoir solution for a final drop volume of 3 μ l. Crystals were obtained and ranged from 200 to 300 μ m in size (see **Figure 2**).

To test for diffraction quality, SHP1 catalytic domain crystals were harvested with nylon loops and then incubated in the presence of 25% PEG10k, 7.5% glycerol, 0.1M HEPES pH 7.5 as cryosolvent, and flash-frozen in liquid nitrogen. X-ray data were collected on Purdue University’s rotating Cu anode source. Complete datasets were obtained at resolutions ranging from 2 – 2.5Å. X-ray data were processed and scaled using HKL2000. Molecular replacement solutions were found for all data sets using the published SHP1 X-ray structure (PDB:1GWZ). These results indicate that the methods described above will produce X-ray structures of the SHP1 catalytic domain suitable for structure-based design and publication.

Table 1: SHP1 construct details

Construct	Sequence	MW
SHP1 Catalytic domain (before His tag removal)	MHHHHHHGVDLGTENLYFQGFWEE FESLQKQEVKNLHQRLEGQRPENKG KNRYKNILPFDHSRVILQGRDSNIPGS DYINANYIKNQLLGPDENAKTYIASQG CLEATVNDFWQMAWQENSRVIVMTT REVEKGRNKCVPYWPEVGMQRAYG PYSVTNCGEHDTEYKLRTLQVSPLD NGDLIREIWHYQYLSWPDHGVPS GGVLSFLDQINQRQESLPHAGPIIVH CSAGIGRTGTIIVIDMLMENISTKGLD CDIDIQKTIQMVRAQRSGMVQTEAQY KFIYVAIAQFIETTKKKLEVLQSQKGG ESEYGNITY	36542.15 Da
SHP1 Catalytic domain (after His tag removal)	GFWEFESLQKQEVKNLHQRLEGQR PENKGNRYKNILPFDHSRVILQGRD SNIPGSDYINANYIKNQLLGPDENAKT YIASQGCLEATVNDFWQMAWQENSR VIVMTTREVEKGRNKCVPYWPEVGM QRAYGPYSVTNCGEHDTEYKLRTL QVSPLDNGDLIREIWHYQYLSWPDH GVPSPPGGVLSFLDQINQRQESLPH AGPIIVHCSAGIGRTGTIIVIDMLMENI STKGLDCDIDIQKTIQMVRAQRSGMV QTEAQYKFIYVAIAQFIETTKKKLEVLQ SQKGGQSEYGNITY	34250.66 Da

Table 2: Buffers for SHP1 expression and purification

Buffer	Component	pH
Super LB (1L)	5g Sodium Chloride 5g Yeast Extract 20g Tryptone 3g Potassium phosphate monobasic 6g Potassium phosphate dibasic	7.2
Carbenicillin (selection marker)	100mg/ml	
Lysis/Binding [Buffer A]	20mM Tris, 500mM NaCl, 5mM Imidazole	8.0
Elution buffer [Buffer B]	20mM Tris, 500mM NaCl, 300mM Imidazole	8.0
Dialysis buffer (2L)	20mM Tris, 150mM NaCl, 5% glycerol and 5mM B-ME	8.0
Sizing/storage buffer	20mM Tris, 150mM NaCl, 1mM TCEP, 5% glycerol	8.0

Figure 1: Summary of SHP1 protein purification procedure. Purity of SHP1 after each step of purification was analyzed using SDS-PAGE (12.5% gels). Lane 1 is the molecular weight standard, followed by cell lysate, insoluble pellet fraction, Ni FT: Flow-through from Nickel IMAC, sample before treatment with TEV protease, after treatment with TEV protease, Rev-Ni FT – fraction after reverse nickel, SEC – sample purity after final step of Size exclusion chromatography. The SEC protein was used for SHP1 protein crystallization.

Figure 2: SHP1 catalytic domain crystals. **Left Panel.** Protein Concentration:12.5 mg/ml Reservoir Solution (Commercial): 1.8M AmSO₄, 0.1M MES Na Salt, Temp = 20 °C Buffer: 20mM Tris, pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 1 mM TCEP Cryosolvent: 25% PEG 10K, 7.5% Glycerol, 0.1M HEPES pH 7.5. **Right Panel.** Protein Concentration:15 mg/ml Reservoir Solution (Commercial): 1.8M AmSO₄, 0.1M MES Na Salt, Temp= 20 °C Buffer: 20mM Tris, pH 8.0, 150 mM NaCl, 5% Glycerol, 1 mM TCEP Cryosolvent: 25% PEG 10K, 7.5% Glycerol, 0.1M HEPES, pH 7.5